

ISic0546

I.Sicily inscription 0546

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR138302

0. [---]

1. [---] Q (uinti) Fabi Caesili Titiani

2. [---]avo Q (uinto) Aquilio Nigro

3. [---p]roco (n) s (uli)

4. Si[cili]ae.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491789

EDR 138302

EDCS 22000873

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7287 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0546. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4384902>